

Highlights

Conceptual design and research on the thermal performance of a martian human base

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- A conceptual design of a Mars human base is proposed to assess its thermal performance
- The climatic zone "tropical" is identified as the most promising region to construct the proposed human base
- Six people could stay 500 days in Mars doing scientific experiments in a three-floor building
- The radiation and thermal insulation from the Martian environment has been shown to be fundamental to maintain comfortable inside temperatures
- Heating power needed has been reduced by selecting an appropriate set of thermal parameters

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Abstract

Human arrival on Mars is one of the most ambitious goals of the various space agencies. Although interest in the planet may appear to be recent, there is ample evidence to show that mankind turned its attention to Mars several centuries ago. However, it was not until the dawn of the space age that this interest shifted from mere speculation to a growing body of scientific and technical information. Unlike Earth, Mars is a planet whose current conditions are not suitable for life of any kind. The main aspects that condition the Martian environment, such as the atmosphere, temperature, radiation and soil, will be briefly analysed. The house of the first inhabitants of the red planet must meet a series of basic requirements, including simplicity, strength and ensuring adequate conditions of habitability and psychological well-being. A conceptual habitat design based on a structure manufactured entirely on Earth is presented. One of the most important challenges engineers of the future will face in the event of a human arrival on Mars is the thermal control of houses. Unlike Earth, the average temperature on Mars is around -60°C , which makes it essential to use very precise thermal control techniques. A theoretical thermal analysis of the designed base will be carried out, checking the influence of a set of parameters, and a particular case will be performed with ESATAN software (a leading tool in the European space sector for ESA missions) together with a sensibility analysis to the thermal model main parameters. The assessment of the location and the daily temperature variation has been analyzed to obtain the best thermal criteria for time-space selection of the base. The results showed the relevance of the insulation of the module with respect to the Mars ground. A thermal insulation method should be implemented in order to ensure the inhabitants' well-being.

Keywords:

Mars exploration, Thermal analysis, Thermal design, Human space, Sensitivity, Uncertainties

1. Introduction

Why Mars? Some scientific papers and articles ask this seemingly simple question [1]. However, its answer is associated with several centuries of constant research, both scientific and technological. Even though Mars is a planet with different characteristics regarding Earth, it is similar in some ways. Over the past half century, with the dawn of the space age, Mars has been the object of most increasing scientific interest. Numerous attempts have been made by major space agencies to obtain a better understanding of this celestial body. In particular, the search for life in it [2, 3, 4] represents a major goal for the present and near future. Thanks to technological progress, we have gone from only being able to view Mars through a telescope to being able to land robots on its surface. And this is only the beginning, as the most ambitious projects are already talking about the arrival of human beings in the coming decades.

1.1. Scope

The space exploration to a solar system body consists of a series of distinct stages, where each of them can be approached as long as the previous stage has been successfully completed. Since this work is focused on the thermal performance of the base, the thermal driver of the design at each exploration stage is also presented in Table 1. In the case of planets exploration, we can consider that the first phase is the placement of a satellite in orbit, or even a fly-by if we want to start from further back. The final phase would be the establishment of a final sustainable colony independent of operations on Earth. The focus of this work is the study of the first human settlement on the surface of Mars. This is a more advanced phase than the current one, as we are in the phase of sending out robotic explorers. Therefore, this work will be affected by a number of limitations due to the simple fact that we do not have available yet the near future technology to come up with an accurate solution. However, the work presented here could be reproduced in future including the innovative advances developed in the space exploration sector.

1.2. Limitations and requirements

The major constraint to build a house on Mars is the planet's environment, which is characterised by a number of factors that require careful selection of both design and materials. These

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Exploration stage	Objectives	Thermal drivers
Planet fly-by	Make first pictures of the surface and/or outermost layers of the atmosphere	Payload in cruise
Orbiter	Make a first study of some characteristics of the planet: atmosphere, radiation, temperature, etc.	Payload in orbit
Lander	Study the entry into the new planet and carry out small studies of its surface	Payload on surface
Rover	Analyze the surface of the planet, the availability of resources and reinforce the work of the orbiter	Payload and rover on surface
Sample surface analyzer	Studying the samples of the planetary surface for a better understanding, which also implies the design of a vehicle capable of making a round trip	Payload and samples on surface
Human first trip support	Shipment of scientific and technological material to prepare the first human settlement	Material on surface and long time
First human settlement	Analyze the habitability of the planet and establish the bases for the development of a future colony	Human on surface
Development of interplanetary vehicles	Manufacture powerful vehicles capable of making round trips between the planet and Earth, as well as transporting the necessary payload	Material and payload in cruise
Expansion of the first settlement	Use the knowledge and technology obtained to expand the number of people and build habitable modules with on-site resources	Human and material on surface
Colony development	Expand the number of inhabitants while establishing a stable transport network and building new habitable modules	Human and material on surface and in cruise
Definitive establishment of the colony	Create a permanent, self-sustaining neighborhood with a well-defined transportation network	Human and material on surface and in cruise

Table 1: Proposal for a sequence of planet exploration stages and main thermal drivers. The time location for the mission analysed in this paper is highlighted.

factors are mainly the temperature, the atmosphere, the radiation and the gravity. In order to cope with all these constraints, the module has to meet a number of essential technical requirements. Its design must be simple and must provide the necessary protection against environmental influences, while at the same time being as cost-effective as possible (i.e. optimising aspects such as the materials used or the living space). Another important aspect is the fulfilment of human requirements [5], i.e. ensuring the well-being of people. Within this group, three requirements categories can be highlighted:

- Biologicals
 1. Ideal temperature
 2. Good humidity levels and a good flow of fresh air
 3. Functional showers and toilets
 4. Controlling light and sound levels
 5. Having space available for food, water, and medicines
 6. Availability of space and equipment for exercise
- Psychologicals
 1. Sufficiently efficient and comfortable living and working environment

2. Facilities easy to maintain and repair
3. Leisure activities, group activities, personal space and adequate lighting

- Socioculturals

1. Possibility to be alone but not isolated
2. Presence of professionals which are not astronauts

1.3. Objectives

The main objective of this work is to perform a general theoretical analysis of the thermal behaviour of a Martian base, conditioned to permit a manned mission of 500 days. To accomplish this, a conceptual design of this base will be proposed and the factors that determine the planet's environment will be briefly explained. The analysis will also be applied to the specific case of the designed base, using ESATAN software. Additional attention is also paid to the radiation protection capacity of the human base. The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, the Mars environment is described according to past references, as well as the assumptions on environmental parameters (used by other designers of Martian surface devices) are reviewed; in section 3 a conceptual design of the Martian base is presented. Later, in section 4, a global thermal analysis of the human base is developed, which is complemented with a particular study case of daily thermal evolution inside the base. Finally, the conclusions are outlined.

2. Mars Environment

In order to establish the boundary conditions on the thermal analysis of the Martian base, this section contains a brief description of Mars atmosphere, temperature, and soil.

2.1. Atmosphere

Mars has a mass approximately ten times smaller than that of the Earth, and consequently, the gravity is also significantly lower. This affects the planet's ability to maintain an atmosphere, which is much more tenuous than Earth's. However, it is not clear the influence of this property on the very low average surface pressure recorded on Mars, which is on the order of one thousandth of that on Earth (6 mbar versus 1 bar). The weak Martian atmosphere, combined with the lack of oceans to help redistribute the solar energy received and the greater distance from the Sun, mean that the differences in surface temperature between day and night are more than noticeable.

Another major difference between the terrestrial and Martian atmospheres is its composition [6]. On Earth, the main components are nitrogen (N_2) and oxygen (O_2). Mars, on the other hand, has an atmosphere dominated by carbon dioxide (CO_2), which, together with the low surface pressure, completely prevents human life. The fact that the atmosphere is mainly composed of CO_2 represents an evolution of the planet that is still a mystery to this day. In this paper, the composition of the Martian air has been considered when calculating the convective heat transfer coefficient from the external surface of the dome and the surrounding air.

The stratification of the Martian atmosphere is quite similar to the terrestrial one [7], although the properties of the layers are quite different from one planet to the other. One of the main differences is that Mars has no stratosphere, as the amount of ozone and aerosols is too small to allow appreciable heating. However, there are certain situations in which the Martian atmosphere harbours high levels of suspended dust. This allows solar radiation to be absorbed and isothermal regions or even thermal inversions to develop near the surface.

A number of rather interesting peculiarities occur in the Martian atmosphere [8]. The first of these is related to the existence of dry CO₂ ice on the polar ice caps. This causes a seasonal cycle of condensation-sublimation between the atmosphere and the ice caps themselves, with condensation being more important in the southern hemisphere due to the high eccentricity of the planet's orbit. This seasonal cycle also causes differences in the surface pressure recorded at the surface, which is highest during perihelion (maximum extent of the south pole) and lowest during aphelion (minimum extent of the south pole). The atmospheric pressure level is considered when estimating the thickness of our base dome.

The second peculiarity of the Martian atmosphere is the variability of the dust content. The dust amount is highest during the summer in the southern hemisphere and varies yearly in a repetitive manner, increasing from solar longitudes slightly above aphelion to solar longitudes slightly above perihelion, and decreasing in the remaining interval. Perihelion is characterised by local dust storms that rarely become global. Because dust effectively absorbs incident solar radiation and absorbs and emits thermal infrared radiation, its implications on the thermal structure and dynamics of the atmosphere are significant, and can produce anomalies not only in the lower layers, but also in the mesosphere and thermosphere. In the thermal analysis presented in section 4, dust over the surface is assumed to reduce the solar incident radiation flux by means of the Beer's law, which considers the dust column optical depth.

2.2. Temperature

The surface temperature on Mars is undoubtedly one of the main factors to be taken into account when designing and manufacturing a base. Its importance lies not only in the properties of the structural materials, but also in the careful choice of thermal control elements. This surface temperature varies from a minimum of about -153°C to a maximum of about 24°C [6], being the average approximately -63°C. The temperature variation in the Martian troposphere is quite different from what occurs on Earth [7]. This is because the scarcity of water vapour causes the temperature variation with height to be very similar to the value of the dry adiabatic gradient, in contrast to the terrestrial troposphere, which is characterised by a combination of dry and wet processes. A similar situation occurs in the mesosphere. As for the thermosphere, the available data are not yet sufficient to be able to characterise it precisely. However, it is known that temperature increases with altitude.

In order to establish the boundaries for our human base thermal model, the distribution of temperatures for the ground, the sky, and the surrounding atmosphere are considered. In [9],

they developed a thermal model of temperature and infrared sensors on board of the Mars 2020 rover, considering separated temperature ranges for summer and winter at a latitude of 26° south. They use minimum temperatures of -103.2°C, -152.4°C, and -101.6°C, and maximum ones of 32.2°C, -85.4°C, and 9.5°C for the ground, the sky, and the atmosphere, respectively. In [10], the spatial and time variations of surface temperature are studied against the near-surface environmental factors, which can be used to estimate the surface temperature variability at a given location and instant.

Also in [10], the spatial aggregation of three Martian surface temperature indicators (sol average temperature, sol temperature range, and sol-to-sol temperature change), were quantitatively evaluated, concluding that their time variation was mainly caused by the thermal inertia and dust. Therefore, the criteria of dividing the Martian surface by similar thermal inertia zones was chosen to do the global thermal study of our human base. A global climate map based on temperature, and modified by topography, albedo, and solar radiation is shown in Fig. 1 from [11].

Fig. 1: Climate zones distribution from [11]. Zone A: Permanent ice cap; B: seasonal winter frost; C: north (mild) Transitional and south (extreme) transitional; D: tropical; E: low albedo tropical; F: subpolar lowland (Basins); G: tropical lowland (Chasmata); and H: subtropical highland (Mountain).

In the glacial zone there exist a permanent ice cap (zone A), while the polar zone is covered by frost during the winter which sublimates during the summer (zone B). Zone C is the north (mild) Transitional and south (extreme) transitional. Zone D is tropical, and zone E is low albedo tropical. Zone F is the subpolar lowland (Basins), zone G is the tropical lowland (Chasmata), and zone H is the subtropical highland (Mountain).

2.3. Soil

The information that exists today about the chemistry and mineralogy of the Martian soil comes from the analyses carried out by the various landers and rovers that have landed on the planet's surface. The first results were obtained by the Viking series, which observed a soil composition rich in magnesium and iron, as well as a sulphur level two orders of magnitude higher than that present in the Earth's crust [12]. Later, it was Mars Pathfinder that was able to make more precise measurements and analyse both soil and rocks [13]. Its studies reinforced the results obtained by the Viking series and confirmed

the presence of oxidised surface materials observed by the orbiters. In terms of radiation, data collected by the Viking rover's Infrared Thermal Mapper (IRTM) were used to determine the thermal emissivity of the Martian surface. By studying various wavelength bands, it was found that the emissivity ranges from 0.9 to 1 [14].

3. Conceptual Design of the Martian Base

3.1. Mission concept

In this subsection, a short system engineering analysis is done with the objective of contextualizing our project. First, the mission concept and a general description of the mission phases will be presented. Then, the functional architecture and the product tree will be listed, to provide a general view of the proposed technical solution.

The core mission concept consists on a settlement in the Martian surface aimed to provide the needed conditioning for human astronauts to operate scientific experimentation campaigns during 500 days. This paper is focused on the conceptual design of the settlement and the thermal analysis of it at different climatic zones of Mars. The mission is divided in several phases:

- Support shipping phase (see Fig. 2): to transport the crane, two surface vehicles, the module in 18 separated parts, the dome, two containers of basics reserves, the solar panels and the antenna.
- Interplanetary phase: to transport the crew to Mars.
- Pre-operational phase: to construct the module, the dome, and the supplementary facilities as the greenhouses.
- Operational phase: to develop the experimental campaigns
- Disposal phase: to disconnect, passivate, and set all the subsystems and equipment to hibernation mode (for next manned trips).
- Return phase: to pick the crew back to Earth.

The mission functional architecture is divided in three levels: 1) system; 2) segments; and 3) elements/facilities. The overall system is compound of the following six segments: a) Earth Ground; b) Launch; c) Interplanetary; d) Mars orbit; e) Mars Ground; and f) User segments. Here, we focus on the Mars Ground Segment, and we breakdown its elements and facilities within the Mars Ground Segment Product Tree. All them are shown in Fig. 2.

3.2. Description of the conceptual design

The human base must be simple and sufficiently resistant to the harsh Martian climate and environment. Therefore, the main structure will be that of the lander itself, as was the case with the Mars Ice House [15, 16]. This allows the lander to settle on the planet without having to resort to prior construction. In this way, a cost reduction is achieved by not needing to use automated robots to carry out this task. However, the fact of

Fig. 2: Artistic view of the Mars Ground Segment, from left to right: crane, lander, surface vehicle 1, solar panels, scientific rover, dome, module, surface vehicle 2, and antenna.

dispensing with this prior construction means that there is an increase in the cost of manufacturing the lander, which could be simpler if the astronauts had a ready-made habitat when they arrived on Mars. For this reason, the DFMA (Design for Manufacturing and Assembly) philosophy will be adopted for the design of the lander, which advocates reducing the number of components and assemblies needed to obtain a certain product as much as possible. Although this philosophy is usually used in the production of simple, standardised parts, an adaptation is sought for the construction of the module. This adaptation consists of conceiving the module as a set of smaller modules assembled in a simple way. The great advantage lies in the fact that these modules will be identical, which allows mass production of the main module. Once the module lands on the surface of Mars, an inflatable membrane (so called dome) will be deployed, as is also the case with the Mars Ice House project [15, 16]. The purpose of this dome is to isolate and protect the main structure from the environment, creating an interior zone with more favourable pressure and temperature conditions. This interior zone could be used for tasks that would otherwise not be possible, such as growing vegetables or studying the environment with sensitive scientific instruments. The dome and the module would be manufactured on Earth. To select the most appropriate dimensions of the simple modules, the NASA Human Research Program (HRP) has been used as a reference [17], which aims to define a "minimum acceptable net habitable volume" for long duration missions. This volume is defined as the minimum required (per person) to ensure the success of a mission with prolonged periods of confinement and isolation in an unfavourable environment. It was concluded that for a mission characterised by a stay on Mars of one and a half years on Earth, this volume should be 25 m³. Consequently, the proposed modular structure will consist of modules in the shape of an isosceles trapezoidal prism, with a volume of 8.4 m³ (see Fig. 3).

Each single module consists of a beam structure made of metal matrix composite material reinforced with silicon carbide particles [18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. This material allows considerable flexibility in the choice of manufacturing method,

Fig. 3: Dimensions (m) of the simple modules.

with stir casting being one of the most cost-effective techniques [23, 24, 25, 26]. The walls and floor of each of the modules will be manufactured by lamination of a metal alloy [19, 20, 22, 27]. This provides a strong and lightweight base. Each of the single modules will have a window in order to meet the various requirements of psychological well-being. This window will have a configuration similar to that of some aircraft, i.e. two sheets of acrylic glass separated by air [28, 29].

The base will consist of three similar hexagonal floors (see Fig. 4). This means that for the construction of each of these floors it will be necessary to assemble six simple modules as the one proposed. One mission concept could be making the part assembly on Earth, but it would also be possible to transport the module parts folded and carry out the final assembly steps on Mars. The main advantage of the latter option is the reduction of the volume occupied in the shipping, but the main disadvantage would be the risk increase of automatic assembly once on Mars.

Fig. 4: Structural configuration of each floor.

Taking into account that the volume of each simple module is 8.4 m^3 and the volume of each of the hexagonal central zones is 16.4 m^3 , the total volume of the module is 200.3 m^3 . This value is higher than the one established in the Human Research Program [17], where a value of 150 m^3 was established for accommodating six people. Furthermore, the 200.3 m^3 are not fully usable, as space reducers such as the various appliances and machines that the module will consist of are not being considered. Besides the three floors, there are two additional areas, which have been referred to as the "upper tank" and the "lower tank". The lower tank would house, for example, the fuel tanks. A possible use of the upper compartment would be to serve as a water storage tank and to house electronic instruments. These uses are only examples, as the study of these compartments is not the objective of this work. Fig. 5 shows an artistic representation of the proposed mars module.

Fig. 5: Closer view of the mars module.

The lower deck would be divided into six compartments (see Fig. 6). Each of these rooms corresponds to each crew member's room. The central area would be a common space, mainly for the storage of clothing and extra-vehicular suits (EVA). The central floor would be divided into five rooms. On one side would be the exercise room, which would consist of various machines and utensils to help maintain the crew's physical condition. In two of the remaining rooms would take place the hygiene area (consisting of toilets and showers). There is also a kitchen and a common area, mainly for washing clothes.

Fig. 6: Inner views of the mars module (left, first floor; center, second floor; and right, third floor).

The upper floor would be divided into four rooms. Firstly, there would be the room for eating and cooking. Secondly, there would be two rooms for leisure and free time. Lastly, there would be the laboratory, from which the crew would carry out the various scientific and technical tasks. The central area would be an annex to the laboratory, where medical activities would also be carried out. Fig. 7 shows an artistic view of the different rooms in the third floor. The connection between the different floors would be made via a vertical staircase, which would link the different central areas. From the central area of each floor it would be possible to access the different rooms on the corresponding floor.

Fig. 7: Third floor rooms (up left, cooking area; up right, living room; down left, laboratory; and down right, medical area).

Access to the base would be via a staircase connecting the central floor with the exterior. The base would be covered by a thin, transparent, semi-spherical dome that would allow it to be isolated from the Martian environment and thus provide more favourable conditions. One of the most attractive materials for this purpose is a polymer called ETFE. Different air chambers would be fabricated to form the dome, which would be attached to the polymer sheets and mounted on a metal structure that would be deployed once the lander reaches the surface [30, 31, 32, 33, 34]. Solar panels would provide the energy needed in the human base, and they would be placed on the Martian surface out of the dome. An estimation of the thickness of the dome membranes to resist the differential pressure was 18 mm from initial structural calculations. The access to this protected intermediate space between the module and the dome would be via decompression chamber.

Besides the Mars Ice House, some other projects were reviewed in order to conceive the conceptual design of our base. MARSHA is a large, cylindrical habitat with four levels developed by AI SpaceFactory [35]. The cylindrical shape responds to the need to withstand internal atmospheric pressure and thermal stresses, and to make the most efficient use of space and facilitate foundation and elevation work. To build this habitat, 3D printing process was selected. The main material is a biopolymer matrix reinforced with basalt fibers that has high compressive and tensile strength, which makes it an interesting

Fig. 8: Inside the dome view (left, staircase access; and right, possible location of a vegetable garden).

alternative even for future terrestrial applications. This habitat has already been proven to be feasible on Earth, but both the procurement of the material and the construction on Mars are unknown. Another project reviewed was Mars X-House, developed by Space Exploration Architecture. The main objective is to improve the current radiation protection combining thermo-plastic, fibrous and cement-derived materials, while also allowing the crew to be integrated with natural light and views of the Martian landscape. Two different versions of the habitat were presented [36, 37]. Both are based on using Martian regolith as a radiation shield, with the difference that one version also uses inflatable modules to protect the inhabitants.

Despite the fact that it seems the most promising option, the reason to not include Martian regolith in our conceptual design is the lack of knowledge on how a habitat can be built with this material, in addition to the fact that this material may have negative repercussions on inhabitants' health.

For all the reasons above mentioned, we selected the human base module-dome concept, which contains some of the strengths of the other ones (efficient use of space, radiation protection,...) while optimizing the construction logistics.

3.3. Radiation protection of the dome and the module

Radiation exposure on the surface of Mars is much more severe than on Earth. This is mainly due to two reasons: 1) the absence of a global Martian magnetic field to deflect energetic charged particles; 2) the presence of a very thin atmosphere. When analysing and quantifying the radiation reaching the planet's surface, three main sources can be distinguished: solar photon radiation (ultraviolet, visible and infrared), cosmic radiation, and radiation caused by energetic solar particles.

The spectrum of solar photon radiation is mainly made up of ultraviolet radiation (<380 nm), visible light ($380 < \lambda < 760$ nm) and infrared radiation (>780 nm) [38]. Of these, ultraviolet radiation is the most important when planning a human mission to Mars, as it is the one that can cause the worst health problems if adequate protection is not provided. The solar ultraviolet irradiance received on the surface of Mars differs significantly from that received on Earth due to the composition of Mars' atmosphere. Wavelengths below 200 nm are absorbed by oxygen in the case of Earth and by carbon dioxide in the case of

Mars. However, the 200-300 nm wavelength range (mainly the UV-C part of the range between 200 and 280 nm) does reach the Martian surface, unlike on Earth, due to the scarcity of ozone in the red planet's atmosphere. The solar flux per wavelength is $0.01 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{nm}^{-1}$ for 200 nm and $0.3 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{nm}^{-1}$ for 300 nm. This is crucial because the UV-C component of the radiation is highly detrimental to the biological processes that govern the development and evolution of all types of organisms. We identify as possible methods to protect the human base against UV radiation those already used in optical lenses and solar cells. These covers are characterized to be transparent, stable and have a greater tolerance to space radiation exposure. Additionally, these coatings must be immune to abrasion and the collection of wind-blown dust. Current investigations go towards the development of complex multi-layer coatings for outer space applications. Typically, instruments that land on the surface of Mars have their windows antireflective (AR) coated and include electrostatic dispersive (ESD) coatings in form of a transparent conducting oxide (TCO) layer (usually, indium-tin oxide (ITO)). However, other materials with better stability are being analysed [39].

Galactic cosmic rays are high-energy particles whose composition is affected by the current point in the solar cycle, although they are mainly composed of protons and atomic nuclei [40]. Their main drawback lies in the difficulty of shielding against them and their ease of penetrating the Martian regolith up to several metres. To study these particles, the Curiosity rover made a series of measurements for 300 sols after its arrival using the RAD (Radiation Assessment Detector) instrument, coinciding with the maximum of Solar Cycle 24. It concludes that the radiation dose rate remains within a fairly stable range between 200 and 220 $\mu\text{Gy/day}$, with certain peaks of higher intensity (associated with a strong solar energetic particle event, SEP) of 260 $\mu\text{Gy/day}$ and lower intensity (associated with interplanetary coronal mass ejections, ICME).

Solar energetic particles are produced in the solar corona as a result of highly energetic processes, mainly associated with outbursts or coronal mass ejections [40]. Such events are sporadic and difficult to predict, and their duration and intensity can vary by several orders of magnitude. However, measurements on Martian surface during several periods of time are available from the RAD instrument, as the proton flux presented in [41].

It is important to analyse the radiation implications for future human missions. Taking as a reference a possible NASA mission design, which assumes a trip to Mars of 180 days and a stay on the planet of 500 days, the total radiation dose received during the mission would be equivalent to approximately 1.01 Sv [42]. This value is not constant, as it is conditioned by the current time of the solar cycle. During a 500-day stay on Mars, the radiation absorbed would be approximately 100 times greater than that absorbed during a year on Earth. A mission to Mars such as the one taken as a reference would practically reach the limit allowed by the various space agencies in terms of radiation exposure. Only to compare, in 500 days on Mars receives around 300 millisieverts while a Radiation worker in Earth receives around 30 millisieverts in the same time. For this reason, it is essential to ensure that the habitable module is built with

the right materials to reduce this level of radiation and allow longer and safer stays on the red planet. To protect against the cosmic radiation and SEP events some guidelines are given in the ECSS standards [43].

Summarizing the radiation description, as depicted in the European Cooperation for Space Standardization (ECSS) about space environment [44] "the radiation environment on the surface of Mars largely derives from the secondary particles produced by cosmic rays and solar protons in the atmosphere and regolith. For manned missions to the planet the dominant particle species of concern is the neutron".

In case of the dome, the material selected (ETFE) presents resistance to aging, and a good mechanical strength and chemical resistance. Apart, the low-weight and flexibility that characterizes it, makes it a good candidate for this purpose.

In case of the external wall of the module, the thickness of aluminium plates is estimated to avoid the penetration of protons and neutrons up to given energy levels. For protons, the radiation protection capacity of aluminum plates is presented in Fig. 9. from [45].

Fig. 9: Penetration depth of electrons and protons through aluminium plates function of the particle energy ([45]).

If the aluminium plate thickness is 25 mm, only protons with more than 80 MeV will penetrate the module wall. On the other hand, according to [41], the proton flux measured on Martian surface during the apparition of the first SEP is the one presented in Fig. 10.

Energetic protons over 135 MeV get the Martian surface easily and their flux is higher than protons with lower energy. Before and after the SEPs arrive at Mars, the penetrating proton surface flux (with proton energies higher than 135 MeV at the surface) was around $0.324 \pm 0.052 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{sr}^{-1}$. Therefore, a bigger value of $0.4 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{sr}^{-1}$ is used to include all protons over 80 MeV, although it should be reminded that the particles lose energy through the aluminium material. Proton flux crossing the wall can be converted to protons dose by graphics like the one in Fig. 11 from [46]. There, the dose absorbed by the shielding material is shown as function of aluminium mass per area. After an iterative process, we consider an aluminium thickness of 20 mm (or 5.54 g/cm^2), at least for the upper roof, and assuming the proton flux from Galactic Cosmic

Rays (GCRs) measured in Martian surface from RAD instrument, the radiation dose passing to the inner side of the module and being potentially absorbed by human beings during the 500 days mission is of 18 millisieverts (around 13 miliseverts/Earth year). In case of SEP events, it would be needed to include a storm shelter by covering one of the first floor rooms with a special shielding protection of about 20 g/cm² to protect the astronauts from protons below 150 MeV.

Fig. 10: Proton flux measured in Martian surface by the RAD instrument ([41]). The constant cosmic radiation and a SEP peak are shown. Penetrating protons: energy over 130 MeV. Stopping protons: below 100 MeV.

Fig. 11: Radiation dose behind an aluminium wall given the thickness ([46]).

RAD neutral particle counter measured 4 Hz in GCRs with peaks of 7.5 Hz during SEPs [41]. Neutrons have a low-interaction with shielding materials, so that will not influence on the decision of the wall thickness. A dedicated protection material both light from Earth or heavy from Martian surface should be investigated (as in [47]), which is out of the scope

of this study. A vertical narrow tank for water surrounding the complete module could be an option of those studies.

4. Description of Thermal Design and Models of the Base

4.1. Thermal model for global assessment of settlement location

To characterize the global thermal performance of the human base as a function of the Mars surface location, a two-nodes model is implemented. As shown in Fig. 12, the system elements represented in the model are: ground, module, inside, dome, outside, and sky. In Fig. 12, it is also shown the heat fluxes exchange between the system elements.

Fig. 12: Scheme of heat exchange between the system elements. Radiative fluxes through the dome are function of dome material: 1) infrared transmissivity of for ground-sky, and module-sky exchange; 2) solar transmissivity for sun-module, and sun-ground exchange.

The list of needed inputs is shown in Table 2, the calculated intermediate variables and outputs in Table 3, and the list of heat power exchanges incorporated to the model is shown in Table 4.

The equation system to be solved and find the module and transparent dome temperatures is:

$$q_{gd} - q_{di} + q'_{md} - q'_{dg} - q'_{ds} + q'_{bsd} + q'_{dsd} + q'_{asd} - q''_o = 0, \quad (1)$$

and:

$$P_h + P_d + q_{gm} - q_{mi} - q'_{mg} - q'_{md} - q'_{ms} + q'_{bsm} + q'_{dsm} + q'_{asm} = 0 \quad (2)$$

In order to make representative thermal analysis, the evolution of thermal environment in the Martian surface along several years (2024 to 2032) is done with the help of [48]. At the moment when Mars is at the perihelion, the winter occurs in the northern hemisphere, while at the aphelion winter is in the southern hemisphere. To search representative hot and cold days during a Martian year (with a climatology estimated from an average solar scenario), maps of maximum and minimum

Input	Model element	Description
L_s		solar longitude angle of Mars (°)
ψ		longitude angle of the base (°)
θ		latitude angle of the base (°)
β		normal-to-surface solar angle (°)
ϵ_m	Module	infrared emmissivity
$\alpha_m(t)$	Module	solar absorptance
A_l	Module	lateral external area [m ²]
A_t	Module	bottom and top area [m ²]
l_{vm}	Module	height [m]
l_{hm}	Module	hexagon side length [m]
P_d	Module	total dissipated power
ϵ_g	Ground	emmissivity
a_g	Ground	Mars albedo
h_{gm}	Ground and Module	Contact conductance [W/m ² K]
h_{gd}	Ground and Dome	Contact conductance [W/m ² K]
$T_g(\psi, \theta, t)$	Ground	temperature [K]
P_{genSP}	Solar Panels	power generated per m ²
$k_i(\psi, \theta, t)$	Inside	air conductivity [W/K m]
ϵ_d	Dome	emmissivity in infrared
α_d	Dome	absorptance in visible
$\tau_{\alpha,d}$	Dome	transmittivity in visible
$\tau_{\epsilon,d}$	Dome	transmittivity in infrared
D_d	Dome	diameter [m]
t_d	Dome	dome thickness [m]
$H_d(\psi, \theta, t)$	Dome	convection coefficient [W/m ² K]
$T_o(\psi, \theta, t)$	Outside	air temperature [K] at an altitude of D_d
$V_o(\psi, \theta, t)$	Outside	wind speed [m/s]
$DoD(\psi, \theta, t)$	Outside	dust column optical depth
$\mu_o(\psi, \theta, t)$	Outside	dynamic viscosity at D_d [Pa s]
$\rho_o(\psi, \theta, t)$	Outside	air density at D_d [Pa s]
$G_{0b}(t)$	Sun	solar irradiance outside the sky [W/m ²]
$G_h(\psi, \theta, t)$	Sun	solar irradiance at ground [W/m ²]
$G_{bh}(\psi, \theta, t)$	Sun	solar direct irradiance at ground [W/m ²]
$G_{dh}(\psi, \theta, t)$	Sun	solar diffusive irradiance at ground [W/m ²]
$T_s(\psi, \theta, t)$	Sky	temperature [K]

Table 2: List of inputs needed for the two-nodes thermal model.

Intermediate	Description	Value
A_m	Module area	$A_l + A_t$
A_i	Inside mid area	$\pi l_{vm}(D_d/2 + l_{hm})$
A_d	Dome area	$\pi D_d^2/2$
GL_{d0}	Dome-outside conductance	$H_d \pi D_d^2/2$
GL_{gd}	Ground-dome conductance	$h_{gd} \pi D_d t_d$
GL_{gm}	Ground-module conductance	$h_{gm} A_t/2$
GL_{di}	Dome-inside conductance	$k_i 2\pi D_d^2/(4D_d/2) = k_i \pi D$
GL_{mi}	Module-inside conductance	$2k_i \pi l_{vm}(D_d + l_{hm})/(D_d - l_{hm})$
GL_{gi}	Ground-inside conductance	$k_i(\pi D_d^2/4 - 6l_{hm}^2 \cos 30/2)/(l_{vm}/2)$
Output	Model element	Description
$P_h(\psi, \theta, t)$	Module	heating power
$P_{gen}(\psi, \theta, t)$	Ground	power to be generated ($P_d + P_h$)
$A_{SP}(\psi, \theta, t)$	Ground	solar panel area (P_{gen}/P_{genSP})
$T_m(\psi, \theta, t)$	Module	temperature
$T_d(\psi, \theta, t)$	Dome	temperature

Table 3: List of output parameters and calculated intermediate variables needed for the two-nodes thermal model.

mean surface temperatures are used, as the one shown in Fig. 13. As commented in subsection 2.2, the division of Martian surface in climate zones is employed to analyze the thermal performance of the human base along each of the zones. Therefore, in the Table 5, the cold and hot reference Mars positions along the year used for each climate zone are presented.

The atmospheric factors included in the global thermal model are the convection heat transfer from the dome to Martian air and the surrounding dust. In case of the dust, the dust column

Heat power	Transfer type	Node 1	Node 2	Value
q_{mi}	conduction	Module	Inside	$GL_{mi}(T_m - T_i)$
q_{di}	conduction	Dome	Inside	$GL_{di}(T_d - T_i)$
q_{gd}	conduction	Ground	Dome	$GL_{gd}(T_g - T_d)$
q_{gm}	conduction	Ground	Module	$GL_{gm}(T_g - T_m)$
q_{gi}	conduction	Ground	Inside	$GL_{gi}(T_g - T_i)$
q'_{md}	infrared radiation	Module	Dome	$\sigma f_{md}(\epsilon_m, \epsilon_d)A_m(T_m^4 - T_d^4)$
q'_{mg}	infrared radiation	Module	Ground	$\sigma f_{mg}(\epsilon_m, \epsilon_d)A_m(T_m^4 - T_g^4)$
q'_{ms}	infrared radiation	Module	Sky	$\sigma f_{ms}(\epsilon_m, \epsilon_d)A_m(T_m^4 - T_s^4)$
q'_{dg}	infrared radiation	Dome	Ground	$\sigma f_{dg}(\epsilon_m, \epsilon_d)A_d(T_d^4 - T_g^4)$
q'_{ds}	infrared radiation	Dome	Sky	$\sigma f_{ds}(\epsilon_m, \epsilon_d)A_d(T_d^4 - T_s^4)$
q'_{bsd}	direct solar radiation	Sun	Dome	$G_{bh} \cos \beta \cdot \alpha_d \cdot \pi D_d^2/4$
q'_{dsd}	diffusive solar radiation	Sun	Dome	$G_{dh} \alpha_d \cdot \pi D_d^2/2$
q'_{dsd}	albedo solar radiation	Sun	Dome	$G_{bh} a_g \alpha_d F_{gd} \cdot \pi D_d^2/2$
q'_{bsm}	direct solar radiation	Sun	Module	$G_{bh} \tau_{\alpha,d} \alpha_m (A_t \cos \beta + A_l \sin \beta)/2$
q'_{dsm}	diffusive solar radiation	Sun	Module	$G_{dh} \tau_{\alpha,d} \alpha_m (A_t/2 + A_l)$
q'_{asm}	albedo solar radiation	Sun	Module	$G_{bh} a_g \tau_{\alpha,d} \alpha_m F_{gm} A_t$
q''_o	convection	Dome	Outside	$H_d A_d (T_d - T_o)$

Table 4: List of heat power interactions within the two-nodes thermal model. The variables F_{ij} are the geometric view factors between two nodes. The functions $f_{ij}(\epsilon_m, \epsilon_d)$ consider the variation of the radiative exchange factor with nodes emmissivity. The rest of variables are described in Tables 2 and 3.

Climate Zone	Cold case: Solar longitude	Hot Case: Solar longitude
	Local time = 00:00	Local time = 12:00
A. North Glacial (90°N)	315	135
A. South Glacial (90°S)	135	255
B. North Polar (67°N)	345	105
B. South Polar (67°S)	165	285
C. North (mild) Transitional (44°N)	285	105
C. South (extreme) Transitional (326°E 26°S)	105	255
D. Tropical (0°E 0°N)	75	195
E. Low albedo tropical (60°E 0°N)	45	195
F. Subpolar Lowland - Basins (60°E 44°S)	75	285
G. Tropical Lowland - Chasmata (60°W 14°S)	75	255
H. Subtropical Highland - Mountain (133°W 19°N)	45	195

Table 5: List of cold and hot reference solar longitudes used for each climate zone.

optical depth at each Martian surface location and at surroundings is employed to calculate the diffusive and direct solar flux. As depicted in [49], we consider the maximum theoretical solar irradiance (G_{0b}) on a horizontal surface outside the atmosphere, which depends on the Mars orbital position given by aerocentric longitude (L_s), and on the latitude of the point (θ). Hereafter, we calculate the contribution percentage between direct and diffuse fluxes at Martian surface, employing L_s , θ , and the value of dust column optical depth (DoD). According to [49], the global irradiance on a horizontal Martian surface is given by (3):

$$G_h = G_{0b} \cos z \cdot \frac{f(z, DoD)}{0.9}, \quad (3)$$

Climate Zone	Cold case temperature [K]	Hot case temperature [K]
A. North Glacial (90°N)	147.7	205.3
A. South Glacial (90°S)	141.5	145.9
B. North Polar (67°N)	150.4	258.8
B. South Polar (67°S)	145.1	287.1
C. North (mild) Transitional (44°N)	161.8	278.1
C. South (extreme) Transitional (326°E 26°S)	166.5	307.6
D. Tropical (0°E 0°N)	182.4	296.0
E. Low albedo tropical (60°E 0°N)	179.1	301.0
F. Subpolar Lowland - Basins (60°E 44°S)	154.0	300.1
G. Tropical Lowland - Chasmata (60°W 14°S)	175.4	302.6
H. Subtropical Highland - Mountain (133°W 19°N)	152.0	290.3

Table 6: List of cold and hot reference surface temperatures used for each climate zone.

Fig. 13: Daily minimum mean surface temperatures during one Martian year for all latitudes at a longitude of 0° (from [48]).

where $f(z, DoD)$ is a function of the sun zenith angle (z) and the dust column optical depth, given in [49]. The direct flux on the Martian surface is:

$$G_{bh} = G_{0b} \cos z \cdot \exp \frac{-DoD}{\cos z}, \quad (4)$$

and, finally, the diffuse flux is obtained as:

$$G_{dh} = G_h - G_{bh} \quad (5)$$

Once the percentage between direct and diffuse solar flux is obtained, the Mars Climate Database [48] is employed to have the global solar irradiance at the Martian surface, so that the effect of the dust storms can be included in the model.

Regarding the convective heat exchange between the dome and the external air, a surface average convective coefficient is computed for the dome as a hemisphere and methodology presented in [50] is followed. The global convective coefficient can be computed from (6).

$$H_d = Nu \frac{k_0}{D_d} \quad (6)$$

The correlation proposed by [51] is followed and used to compute the Nusselt number outside the dome (7). A constant

dynamic viscosity is considered to simplify the model.

$$Nu = 2 + (0.4Re^{\frac{1}{2}} + 0.06Re^{\frac{2}{3}})Pr^{0.4} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{\mu_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad (7)$$

Finally, thermal conductivity outside the dome must also be computed as it is not included in the database of [48]. For this purpose, a regression Equation (8) is used as proposed in [52]. This regression equation is derived from data from MegaWatSoft [53], where properties of CO₂ are presented for different ambient conditions.

$$k_0 = 1.1691 \times 10^{-7} T_0^2 + 1.3327 \times 10^{-5} T_0 + 2.2469 \times 10^{-3} \quad (8)$$

4.2. Detailed thermal model for daily thermal evolution

Once the global stationary thermal study of two nodes has been carried out, a more detailed model is developed for studying transient cases on a particular location of the Martian surface. According to the assessment of results from the previous global two-nodes model, a specific configuration of the different parameters presented throughout the text is chosen. The ESATAN software, a tool used by the European Space Agency in the design of its space missions, has been used to achieve this solution. The first step is to select the configuration, dimensions and occupation of the base. The study will be carried out taking as a reference the base exposed as the conceptual design. This means that each of the simple modules will be a trapezoidal prism, the main dimensions of which are: larger base 4.5 m, smaller base 1.5 m, height 2.8 m. There will be a total of three floors, which an interior layout as the presented above. The combination of these two conditions implies that the module will therefore be a regular hexagonal prism with base side 4.5 m and height 8.4 m, as shown in Fig. 14. The dome protecting the module is a semi-sphere with a radius of 12m. The occupation of the base will be 6 inhabitants.

The next step is to define the geometry of the base in the software. This geometry will be composed of:

- Rectangles: used in the definition of the floors of the different levels, the outer walls and the inner walls.
- Triangles: used in the definition of the floors of the different levels, in order to obtain the hexagonal geometry.
- Sphere: used in the definition of the transparent dome.

A material and an optical coating must be assigned to each component of the geometry, which will be defined by a number of bulk and optical properties, as shown in Table 7. The assignment would be:

- Floors: aluminium alloy as material, white paint as optical coating.
- Inner walls: aluminium alloy as material, white paint as optical coating.
- Outer walls: aluminium alloy as material, black paint as coating. In addition, each consists of a central area with acrylic glass as material, thus representing windows.

- Transparent membrane: ETFE as material.

The decision to use white paint for the interior and black paint for the exterior is based on the different optical properties of each one. Because of the low temperatures on Mars, the high absorptivity of the black paint is of interest, as well as the heat retention in the interior, favoured by the high emissivity of the white paint.

Fig. 14: From left to right, geometry development sequence in ESATAN.

Material	Properties	Optical Coating	Properties
ETFE	$\rho=1700 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $k=0.24 \text{ W/m}^*\text{K}$ $c=1172 \text{ J/g}^*\text{K}$	ETFE	$\alpha=0.1$ $\epsilon=0.89$ $\tau_\epsilon = 0.11$
Acrylic glass	$\rho=1180 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $k=0.2 \text{ W/m}^*\text{K}$ $c=1500 \text{ J/g}^*\text{K}$	Acrylic glass	$\alpha=0.1$ $\epsilon=0.94$ $\tau_\epsilon = 0.1 / \tau_\alpha = 0.9$
Aluminium alloy	$\rho=2700 \text{ kg/m}^3$ $k=181.5 \text{ W/m}^*\text{K}$ $c=889.5 \text{ J/g}^*\text{K}$	White / Black paint	$\alpha=0.24 / \alpha=0.88$ $\epsilon=0.9 / \epsilon=0.88$

Table 7: Mechanical and optical properties defined in ESATAN.

After completing the creation of the geometry, the next step is to define the boundary conditions that will govern the study. In order to properly implement these conditions in the model, it would be necessary to define each of the appliances and instruments inside the module, which will inject heat dissipation in the thermal model. Non-geometric thermal nodes are defined to approximate the behaviour of these elements, at least one node for each boundary condition. In addition, it is also essential to place each of these nodes in its corresponding compartment within the module. The definition of boundary conditions can be seen in Table 8. Note that the values specified are approximations that allow a decent representation of reality.

To complete the thermal model in ESATAN, it is also needed to define the couplings between the nodes. These couplings allow the representation of the type of heat transfer that occurs between the different nodes of the geometry. Two types of couplings will be used: radiative and conductive couplings. Each of the defined non-geometric thermal nodes is radiatively coupled to the surrounding walls, floor and ceiling of the compartment in which it is located. In this way, the effect of the power dissipation of the various appliances and instruments as well as the effect of the presence of the inhabitants of the base can be represented. On the other hand, the conductive couplings are used for the heat transfer calculation by conduction. Again, all non-geometric thermal nodes representing appliances and instruments are also conductively coupled to the wall with which they are in contact.

Node number	Boundary condition	Location	Value
1-21	Average heat generated by a human being when at rest	One in each module compartment	Depends on how many inhabitants are in each compartment. Possible values: 80/160/240/320/400/480 W (each node) 36.5 °C (each node)
22-24	Average human body temperature Average heat generated by a human being when doing sport	One in each module compartment One in each gym compartment	Depends on how many inhabitants are in each gym compartment. Possible values: 300/600 W (each node)
25	Temperature reached in the showers when using them	Showers	30 °C
26	Power dissipated by the exercise bike	Gym	600 W
27	Power dissipated by the treadmill	Gym	1800 W
28-30	Power dissipated by household appliances at breakfast, lunch and dinner time	Kitchen	1700/5600/3800 W (respectively)
31	Power dissipated by the fridge and the freezer	Kitchen	480 W
32,33	Power dissipated by hygiene instruments	One in each bathroom compartment	1000 W (each node)
34,35	Power dissipated by the working instruments in the laboratory	One in each laboratory compartment	4900 W (each node)
36	Power dissipated by the washing machine and the tumble dryer	Central zone of the second floor	760 W
37	Power dissipated by the iron	Central zone of the third floor	1000 W
38,39	Power dissipated by leisure instruments	One in each leisure compartment	350 (each node)

Table 8: Definition of the boundary conditions.

Additionally, the linear conductors between the dome and the ground, and between the module and the ground have been defined. In fact, these conductors, as well as the dome and module optical properties are the main parameters used to regulate the temperature inside the module. The rest of coupling are automatically calculated by ESATAN.

Once the couplings have been defined, we define the radiative environment that will be used as a reference for the thermal calculations. The definition of this environment makes possible to calculate variables such as direct heat flows or heat flows absorbed by the base components. The calculation method used is the Monte Carlo ray tracing method (MCRT), which calculates radiative couplings and heat fluxes by means of a ray tracing procedure that considers the individual history of thermal radiation energy packets from the point of emission to the point of absorption. These energy packets can follow infinite paths. As it is not possible to follow the trajectory of an infinite number of rays, the method estimates the radiative couplings and heat fluxes by averaging the results obtained from a finite random sample of rays. The parameters to be defined in the radiative environment are the thermal, geometric and mass properties of the Sun-Mars system. The solar declination is directly related to the solar longitude and therefore depends on the position of

Mars in the orbit as shown in Equation (9).

$$\sin D_s = \sin \epsilon \cdot \sin L_s \quad (9)$$

For the cold and hot cases studied in the simplified model, the solar longitudes of $L_s = 75^\circ$ and $L_s = 195^\circ$ were used respectively.

The position of the base on the surface of the planet is set to a latitude of 0° . This value has been chosen for two main reasons: 1) the presence of relatively moderate temperatures (as demonstrated with the results of stationary study in section 5.1); and 2) the possibility of obtaining water from the subsoil. After the steady cases were analyzed, it was decided to study the daily evolution of the thermal conditions for a martian surface longitude of 0° within the Tropical climatic zone. Regarding the orientation of the base, it is established that the vertical axis of the module points to the zenith (see Fig. 15).

Fig. 15: Representation of the radius vector joining Mars and the Sun in the cold case, as well as the location and orientation of the base.

In the transient cases studied, the methodology followed is as follows:

- Divide the Martian day into time slots. Making use of the similar duration of the Martian and terrestrial day, human bio-rhythm can be maintained, and dividing the Martian day in time slots representing common activity situations within the module. The objective is to study the temperature evolution in the rooms where the activity occurs in each of the time slots, taking into account the corresponding boundary conditions (see Table 9).
- Define temperature sensors. To be able to evaluate the temperature inside the module, it is necessary to define non-geometric thermal nodes without any associated boundary condition to avoid distorted results. Each of these sensors must be coupled conductively and radiatively with the non-geometric thermal nodes, walls, floor and ceiling of the room in which they are located, so that the result obtained is as realistic as possible.
- Study the evolution of the temperature in the sensors. For each defined time slot, temperature evolution graphs shall be obtained for the sensors located in the rooms corresponding to each case.

- Define heaters. The nature of the Martian climate makes completely impossible to survive at the base without a heating system. One heater per room is defined as a boundary condition. The objective is to find a power that allows the establishment of temperatures suitable for human survival (between 20 and 25°C) in each room of the module. As a hypothesis, it is considered that each heater operates only in the time slot to which it belongs, assuming that during the rest of the day there is no activity in the room.
- Re-evaluate the temperature evolution in the sensors. The analysis is repeated by adding the boundary conditions of the heaters and the temperature evolution graphs are obtained again. The study of each time slot is finished when the temperature recorded at the corresponding sensors remains approximately constant over the time interval studied.

Time slot	Activity	Involved probes
00:00-06:00	The 6 inhabitants sleep in their rooms	Bedrooms of the six inhabitants
06:00-07:00	Some inhabitants do sport in the gym while others take a shower	Gym and showers
07:00-08:00	Inhabitants have breakfast and perform the necessary hygiene activities before starting their day	Kitchen and bathrooms
08:00-14:00	Inhabitants work in the laboratory	Laboratory
14:00-15:00	Lunch time	Kitchen
15:00-18:00	Inhabitants work in the laboratory	Laboratory
18:00-20:00	Wash clothes or iron	Central zones of second and third floor
20:00-21:00	Dinner time	Kitchen
21:00-23:00	Leisure time	Leisure rooms
23:00-24:00	The 6 inhabitants sleep in their rooms	Bedrooms of the six inhabitants

Table 9: Time slots employed to do the thermal analysis.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Global assessment of base thermal performance

The main results obtained from the simple model with two nodes are presented in this section. In Fig. 16, the temperatures of the sky, the surrounding air, and the Martian surface at the reference location of each climatic zone are shown. Together with boundary temperatures, the initial calculation of the module temperature before the application of any heating power is also shown in Fig. 16. It can be observed that the calculated module temperature is higher than the environmental temperatures in most climatic zones, except in cold cases of icing polar and frost regions (zones A and B) in the northern and southern hemispheres, where the module temperature is as cold as the Martian surface and the air. In the other cold cases, the module temperature at least equates the surface temperature. In the hot cases, the module temperature is over the environmental ones, which can be explained thanks to the solar energy absorbed by the dome.

Fig. 16: Boundary temperatures of sky, surrounding air, and Martian surface, vs module temperatures before applying heating power to the human base ($T_{m,nh}$), for all climatic zones.

To gain confidence in such a 2-nodes model, once the formulation is programmed, a variability analysis for the module temperature has been developed. This consists on solving the equation system for each climatic zone case, and by using the temperature results as reference, to estimate the derivative of the module temperature with respect to each thermal parameter. This is shown in Fig. 17 for climate zones A and B, Fig. 18 for zones C, D, and E, and Fig. 19 for zones F, G, and H. As the temperature reached by the module in any case is very low from the human perspective, the mentioned derivative should be positive, to consider the thermal parameter changes are convenient to warm the human base. Moreover, the values of parameters with negative derivatives should be decreased to increase the global temperature of the module. For instance, in the three figures mentioned, it can be seen that the contact conductance between the module and the ground, h_{gm} , produces a negative derivative, so that its value would be reduced to warm the module. However, the influence of contact conductance between the dome and the ground is negligible to change the module temperature. On the other hand, it is also shown that to increase the solar absorptance, α_m , and to reduce the emissivity of the module, ϵ_m , is benefit in any case. A similar conclusion can be extrated from dome transmittivity, thus, in the solar range $\tau_{\alpha,d}$ benefits the module warming and in the infrared range $\tau_{\epsilon,d}$ prejudices. Finally, the larger is the human base the colder is its temperature.

According to the scale of Fig. 17 with respect to Figs. 18 and 19, any parameter change is more effective in polar and frost regions A and B than at warmer latitudes, due to the very low module temperature level. However, as shown later, the heating power needed to maintain comfortable temperatures in zones A and B makes the thermal solution unfeasible.

In order to optimize the amount of heating power required for each location, variability has been allowed in the most critical parameter, the conductance to the ground, h_{gm} , has been allowed to adopt different values. In this simple model this

Fig. 17: Variability of the module temperature with thermal parameters, for climatic zones A and B.

Fig. 18: Variability of the module temperature with thermal parameters, for climatic zones C, D and E.

Fig. 19: Variability of the module temperature with thermal parameters, for climatic zones F, G and H.

variation is translated as numerical, but it would imply different mounting concepts for the same general structure. The procedure to minimize power has been the following: for each location, the value of h_{gm} is adjusted as the minimum value that would allow human tolerable temperatures for the hot case (as it is always more efficient to warm than to cool an ambient). Then, this h_{gm} value is used in the cold case (same mounting system per location) and the power needed in order to keep human rated temperature is calculated. After these, the necessary solar panel area taking into account the local weather conditions in the cold case is calculated.

The results of this solar panel area minimization are shown in Fig. 20. The values of h_{gm} for each zone are depicted in yellow (scale on the left-most vertical axis in W/m^2K), and the total power dissipated in the base in blue (also scale on the left-most vertical axis in kW). The necessary solar panel area is shown as a red dot (right hand side scale). It should be pointed out that for the most extreme latitudes, there is no sunlight in winter, and the red dot is on the maximum value of the scale (AN and AS). For these latitudes, this base would have to be combined with another technology, such as RTG in safety conditions.

Fig. 20: Ground contact conductance (h_{gm}), heating power (P_h) and solar panel required area (A_{sp}), for all climatic zones

In Fig. 21, the temperatures of the module at the reference location of each climatic zone are shown before and after the application of the heating power, which is also presented in the same figure.

According to the power levels required to warm the base in cold cases (see Fig. 21), we can divide the climate zones in three categories: 1) high heating power for north polar (AN), south polar (AS), south frost (BS), and subpolar lowlands (F); 2) medium heating power for north frost (B), north and south transitional zones (CN and CS), and tropical low land (G); 3) normal heating power for the tropical (D), the low albedo tropical (E), and the subtropical highland (H). Latter category is the most suitable for the construction of this type of human base as expected according to temperatures and dust storms distribution on Mars.

Fig. 21: Temperatures before ($T_{m,nh}$) and after ($T_{m,h}$) applying heating power (P_h) to the human base.

5.2. Daily evolution of base thermal performance

During this section, the results obtained from the thermal model built on ESATAN are presented, starting with an initial assessment of the power required at the martian base along one representative day.

Time slot	Compartment	Dissipated power
00:00-06:00	Bedrooms	0 W
06:00-07:00	Showers	1000 W
	Gym	7000 W
07:00-08:00	Kitchen	1000 W
08:00-14:00	Laboratory	15000 W
14:00-15:00	Kitchen	1000 W
15:00-18:00	Laboratory	7500 W
18:00-20:00	Cleaning	7500 W
20:00-21:00	Kitchen	1000 W
21:00-23:00	Leisure rooms	1000 W
23:00-24:00	Bedrooms	0 W

Table 10: Required heat power obtained for every heater to ensure the temperature requirements proposed under the assumptions made.

In view of the results for each of the slots, it should be noted that the power values obtained for each of the heaters are not constant during the entire time interval that they are active, as there will come a time when a suitable temperature is reached and it will not be necessary to maintain the same heat dissipation to guarantee habitability conditions in the room in which they are located. A clear example is the heaters in the laboratory or leisure rooms. These heaters require high power in order to reach adequate temperatures. However, once these temperatures are reached, it would not be necessary to maintain the high energy input. It therefore follows that the values obtained correspond to the maximum energy input of each heater. It is emphasised again that the results obtained are based on the assumption that each heater is active only in its corresponding slot.

From Fig. 22 one can clearly see how the intermediate floor is the one that benefits the most from reaching a higher temperature. It is the first and last floors that are subject to the greatest

loss of energy in the form of heat and, therefore, a greater use of power is required to maintain their habitability.

Fig. 22: Temperature evolution per floor along a representative day in the martian base, for both the cold and hot case scenarios.

If we refer to the programmed timetable from Table 9 and the room distribution in Fig. 6, we can see that temperatures are lower for both sleeping and working activities, to ensure greater comfort. In contrast, temperatures are higher for activities developed on the first floor, ensuring a more comfortable environment, since it has been conceived to rest.

The next step was to perform a sensitivity analysis on the main parameters from the mathematical model. For this purpose, the SEA method has been employed. SEA is a fast and simple method to implement, but it requires working under several assumptions for the thermal model. These are:

- The models must be linear (or linearisable).
- The parameters must be statistically independent.
- The probability distributions of the parameters must be normally distributed.

As thermal models are non-linear and there are multiple possible probability distributions, results are expected to deviate from more accurate solutions [54]. Nevertheless, it has an important advantage, which is that it allows to evaluate the individual contribution of each parameter to the total uncertainty, the latter being obtained as a quadratic sum of the previous ones.

If $T = f(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is a linear function of n independent variables, each of them normally distributed, then T is also normally distributed, and the relationship between the interval for the variables w_i and the interval for the result w_T that gives the same odds both for each of the variables and for the results given by:

$$w_T = \left[\left(\frac{\partial f(\mu_1, \dots, \mu_n)}{\partial x_1} w_1 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial f(\mu_1, \dots, \mu_n)}{\partial x_n} w_n \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

In Table 11, the lowest and highest temperature at the three different floors is presented for both the cold and hot cases, respectively (extracted from Fig. 22).

Cold case			Hot case		
μ_{T1}	μ_{T2}	μ_{T3}	μ_{T1}	μ_{T2}	μ_{T3}
11.735	20.287	13.920	27.144	32.903	22.292

Table 11: Nominal coldest and hottest temperatures per floor (temperatures in °C).

To implement this formulation, a 1% variation from the nominal value of each parameter under study has been applied. Also, an uncertainty has been associated to each parameter, depending on its nature (and according to the recommendations given by the ECSS standards [55]). The main properties selected and the results obtained are presented in Tables 12 and 13. It can be clearly seen how one of the factors that have the greatest influence on the results is the variation of h_{gm} , the ground-module contact, being able to vary in almost 20 °C the first floor temperature in the cold case scenario. Therefore, special attention should be paid to the insulation of the module to minimise heat losses through the ground.

Property	Nominal value	Uncertainty (%)	w_{T1}	w_{T2}	w_{T3}
$\alpha_{BlackPaint}$	0.860	15.0	0.114	0.160	0.153
$\epsilon_{BlackPaint}$	0.240	15.0	8.210	10.018	8.839
$\alpha_{WhitePaint}$	0.240	15.0	0.395	0.496	0.457
$\epsilon_{WhitePaint}$	0.900	15.0	1.965	2.552	1.456
ϵ_d	0.850	15.0	0.425	0.898	2.551
α_d	0.730	15.0	0.021	0.043	0.092
$\tau_{\epsilon,d}$	0.110	15.0	0.689	0.986	1.465
$\tau_{\alpha,d}$	0.900	15.0	0.279	0.592	1.044
h_{gm}	3.000	100.0	19.648	8.031	4.014
h_{str}	1.000	100.0	2.083	1.746	1.171
h_{gd}	250.000	100.0	0.008	0.010	0.010
k_{air}	0.024	10.0	0.361	0.282	0.161
d_{air}	1.500	25.0	0.858	0.637	0.330
t_m	0.500	25.0	0.002	0.003	0.002
Total			21.527	13.316	10.385

Table 12: SEA sensitivity cold case computation.

Property	Nominal value	Uncertainty (%)	w_{T1}	w_{T2}	w_{T3}
$\alpha_{BlackPaint}$	0.860	15.0	0.471	0.227	0.035
$\epsilon_{BlackPaint}$	0.240	15.0	2.375	3.875	2.125
$\alpha_{WhitePaint}$	0.240	15.0	0.754	0.265	0.033
$\epsilon_{WhitePaint}$	0.900	15.0	0.562	1.269	0.216
ϵ_d	0.850	15.0	0.071	0.141	0.847
α_d	0.730	15.0	0.001	0.041	0.043
$\tau_{\epsilon,d}$	0.110	15.0	3.136	0.818	0.273
$\tau_{\alpha,d}$	0.900	15.0	0.667	1.300	2.817
h_{gm}	3.000	100.0	4.419	0.544	0.344
h_{str}	1.000	100.0	2.691	1.066	0.279
h_{gd}	250.000	100.0	0.012	0.298	1.163
k_{air}	0.024	10.0	0.105	0.542	0.564
d_{air}	1.500	25.0	0.444	1.694	1.824
t_m	0.500	25.0	0.003	0.074	0.291
Total			6.634	4.881	4.309

Table 13: SEA sensitivity hot case computation.

6. Conclusions

Mars human exploration is included in the agenda of all space agencies for near future. However, to achieve the confidence needed to embark human beings in such a mission, many issues are open to find the appropriate solutions. One of them is the human base concept, which should assure the survival of its cohabitants. In this paper, a module-dome base concept for the first manned trip to Mars has been proposed, and its main characteristics described. One of the main drivers, which is the thermal performance of the base has been analyzed for different Mars climatic zones. First, steady state studies in worst hot and cold conditions indicated the relevant thermal parameters. Lately, a more detailed model of the base for the Tropical zone was done with ESATAN software.

The results of the two-nodes thermal model and ESATAN sensitivity computation showed that special attention should be put to the thermal insulation of the module with respect to the Mars ground. Thus, the thermal contact conductance between the module and the ground has to be minimized by means of insulating materials or subsystems. An initial radiation protection analysis against protons would lead to a module thickness of 20 mm, but further investigation is needed to protect against neutrons.

The detailed thermal model showed that the analysis of the power consumption for heating each of the floors according to the timetable maintained by the inhabitants is essential in order to ensure a comfortable temperature throughout the day.

An initial optimization was performed using the two node model, but the next steps in the future work should begin by performing a selection of different acclimatization methods (air re-circulation, heat pipes, etc) and after this a full parameter optimization should be performed. However, this is too detailed for the scope of this work, which is oriented towards conceptual design more than detailed design.

And as subsequent step in this line of future work, a ground test campaign is in place. As it has been shown in the document, the key parameters are the conductive coupling to the ground and the optical surface properties of the base. These parameters have large inherent uncertainties, which should be measured through ground tests. A full scale model test is unlikely due to dimensions, but scaled models should be tested in gaseous thermal chambers (that can adjust pressure in order to simulate the martian atmosphere). These tests should also include a soil base which thermally reproduces the martian terrain in order to test different base mount configurations. These should reduce uncertainty of all the mentioned parameters. Additionally it would also serve as input information to model the martian soil of the thermal model below the dome, which currently is a boundary node, which is a conservative assumption, and this may lead to more margin in the design. Additionally, a campaign of mechanical assembly tests may be performed, in order to test the mechanical concepts, such as the dome folding and unfolding and the efficiency of the different floor stack and setup.

This work may be used as a baseline for future missions to Mars, thanks to being able to identify the main factors con-

tributing to the development of scientific activities on a human Martian base. Further research will be required to develop a more detailed analysis in order to optimise the power consumption.

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References

- [1] M. Murthy, A home on mars?, *Science Reporter* 57 (2020) 22–25, <http://nopr.niscair.res.in/handle/123456789/55029>.
- [2] C. McKay, An origin of life on mars, *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology* (April 2010). doi:10.1101/cshperspect.a003509.
- [3] R. Joseph, R. Dass, V. Rizzo, N. Cantasano, G. Bianciardi, Evidence of life on mars?, *Journal of Astrobiology and Space Science Reviews* 1 (2019) 40–81.
- [4] G. Bianciardi, K. Wolowski, R. del Gaudio, Is there life on mars? where is the proof?, *Journal of Astrobiology* 7 (2021) 38–75.
- [5] C. Bogdhan, A. Breaum, H. Breum, H. Larsen, M. Lovenskjold, In-situ habitat design on mars, *Thirdroom*, <https://ruc-thirdroom.dk/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/In-situ-Habitat-Design-on-Mars.pdf> (December 2019).
- [6] Comparing the atmosphere of mars and earth, *European Space Agency*, <https://www.esa.int/esearch?q=martian+atmosphere> (April 2018).
- [7] R. Zurek, J. Barnes, R. Haberle, J. Pollack, J. Tillman, C. Leovy, *Dynamics of the atmosphere of mars*, in: *Mars (A93-27852 09-91) Conference Proceedings*, University of Arizona Press, 1992, pp. 835–933.
- [8] F. González, *Modelos energéticos, químicos y dinámicos de la alta atmósfera de marte*, Ph.D. thesis, Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía, Universidad de Granada (2006).
- [9] I. Perez-Grande, L. Peinado, T. I. Chamorro, A., G. Alonso, Thermal design of the air temperature sensor (ats) and the thermal infrared sensor (tirs) of the mars environmental dynamics analyzer (meda) for mars 2020, in: *In Proc. 47th International Conference on Environmental Systems*, July 16–20, 2017.
- [10] Y. Luo, J. Yan, F. Li, B. Li, Spatial autocorrelation of martian surface temperature and its spatio-temporal relationships with near-surface environmental factors across china's tianwen-1 landing zone, *Remote Sensing* 13(11) (2021) 2206. doi:10.3390/rs13112206.
- [11] H. Hargitai, Mars climate zone map based on tes data, recovered on October 2021 from <http://planetologia.elte.hu/mcdd/climatemaps.html>.
- [12] A. Yen, R. Gellert, C. Schröder, et. al, An integrated view of the chemistry and mineralogy of martian soils, *Nature* 436 (2005) 49–54. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature03637>.
- [13] J. Bell III, H. McSween Jr., J. Crisp, R. Morris, et. al, Mineralogic and compositional properties of martian soil and dust: Results from mars pathfinder, *Journal of Geophysical Research* 105 (2000) 1721–1755. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/1999JE001060>.
- [14] P. Christensen, Thermal emissivity of the martian surface: Evidence for compositional variations, in: *Lunar And Planetary Science*, Vol. 15, 1984, pp. 150–151.
- [15] Mars ice house, *Clouds Architecture Office*, recovered on March 2021 from <https://cloudsao.com/MARS-ICE-HOUSE>.
- [16] Mars ice house, *Space Exploration Architecture (SEARCH+)*, recovered on March 2021 from <http://www.spacearch.com/mars-ice-house>.
- [17] A. Whitmire, L. Leveton, H. Broughton, M. Basner, A. Kearney, Minimum acceptable net habitable volume for long-duration exploration missions subject matter expert consensus session report, 2014.
- [18] K. Hemalatha, K. Ashokkumar, G. Gautham, P. Aurlpandiyam, V. Venkatachalapathy, Wear analysis of aluminium 7075/sic metal matrix composites, *International Journal of Advanced Research in Basis Engineering Sciences and Technology* 3 (2017) 62–68.

- [19] Matmach, recovered on April 2021 from <https://matmatch.com/>.
- [20] Matweb, recovered on April 2021 from <http://www.matweb.com/>.
- [21] S. Rawal, Metal-matrix composites for space applications, *The journal of the Minerals, Metals and Materials Society* 53 (2001) 14–17. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-001-0139-z>.
- [22] K. Suryanarayanan, R. Praveen, S. Raghuraman, Silicon carbide reinforced aluminium metal matrix composites for aerospace applications: A literature review, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology* 2 (2013) 6336–6344.
- [23] F. Campbell, *Manufacturing Technology for Aerospace Structural Materials*, 1st Edition, Elsevier Ltd., 2006.
- [24] J. Dixon, S. Logasarathy, Fabrication of al7075 metal matrix composite through stir casting method - a review, *International Journal of Engineering Research Technology* (May 2019).
- [25] R. Gangaram Bhandare, P. Sonawane, Preparation of aluminium matrix composite by using stir casting method, *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology* 3 (2013) 61–65.
- [26] A. Pal, S. Swaroop Saxena, A. Verma, B. Chandra Kandpal, Stir casting of metal matrix composites - a review, *International Journal of Computer Mathematical Sciences* 4 (2015) 1–3.
- [27] Airware 2050-t84 plate, Constellium, recovered on May 2021 from <https://www.constellium.com/sites/default/files/markets/>.
- [28] T. Bhattacharya, M. Sanoja, Material selection for aircraft windows, Tech. rep., University of Pittsburgh (November 2010). doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16925.31207.
- [29] R. Hedayati, S. Ziaei-Rad, A. Eyvazian, A. Hamouda, Bird strike analysis on a typical helicopter windshield with different lay-ups, *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology* 28 (2014) 1381–1392. doi:10.1007/s12206-014-0125-3.
- [30] Dupont tefzel etfe. fluoroplastic film, Pronat Industries, recovered on June 2021 from <https://pronatindustries.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/DuPont-ETFE-Film.pdf>.
- [31] H. Liu, B. Li, Z. Chen, T. Zhou, Q. Zhang, Solar radiation properties of common membrane roofs used in building structures, *Materials Design* 105 (2016) 268–277. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2016.05.068.
- [32] A. Mainini, T. Poli, R. Paolini, M. Zinzi, L. Vercesi, Transparent multi-layer etfe panels for building envelope: Thermal transmittance evaluation and assessment of optical and solar performance decay due to soiling, *Energy Procedia* 48 (2014) 1302–1310. doi:10.1016/j.egypro.2014.02.147.
- [33] C. Monticelli, A. Campioli, A. Zanelli, Environmental load of etfe cushions and future ways for their self-sufficient performances, in: A. Domingo, C. Lázaro (Eds.), *Evolution and Trends in Design, Analysis and Construction of Shell and Spatial Structures*, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia, Spain, 2009.
- [34] S. Piontini, Towards a transparent photovoltaic film. a technological approach with the etfe, Ph.D. thesis, Facoltà di Architettura e Società (2011).
- [35] Marsha, AI SpaceFactory, recovered on March 2021 from <https://www.aispacefactory.com/marsha>.
- [36] Mars x-house v1, Space Exploration Architecture (SEArch+), recovered on March 2021 from <http://www.spacexarch.com/marsxhousev1>.
- [37] Mars x-house v2, Space Exploration Architecture (SEArch+), recovered on March 2021 from <http://www.spacexarch.com/mars-xhouse-v2>.
- [38] C. Córdoba, Radiación ultravioleta solar en marte: Implicaciones biológicas y búsqueda de ambientes potencialmente habitables, Sociedad Española de Medicina Aeroespacial, <https://www.semae.es/wp-content/uploads/MARte-y-UV-Rad.pdf> (November 2004).
- [39] S. Pellicori, C. Martinez, D. Wilt, Development and testing of coatings for orbital space radiation environments, *Applied optics* 53 (2014) A339–50. doi:10.1364/AO.53.00A339.
- [40] D. Hassler, C. Zeitlin, R. Wimmer-Schweingruber, B. Ehresmann, S. Rafkin, J. Eigenbrode, et. al, Mars’ surface radiation environment measured with the mars science laboratory’s curiosity rover, *Science* 343 (6169) (January 2014). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1244797>.
- [41] B. Ehresmann, D. M. Hassler, C. Zeitlin, J. Guo, R. F. Wimmer-Schweingruber, D. Matthä, et al., Energetic particle radiation environment observed by rad on the surface of mars during the september 2017 event, *Geophysical Research Letters* 45 (2018) 5305–5311. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2018GL077801>.
- [42] C. Zeitlin, D. Hassler, B. Cucinotta, R. Ehresmann, et. al, Measurements of energetic particle radiation in transit to mars on the mars science laboratory, *Science* 340 (2013) 1080–1084. doi:DOI: 10.1126/science.1235989.
- [43] ECSS Secretariat, Ecss-e-hb-10-12a: Calculation of radiation and its effects and margin policy handbook (Dec 2010).
- [44] ECSS Secretariat, Ecss-e-st-31c: Space engineering - space environment (Nov 2008).
- [45] H. Garrett, A. Whittlesey, *Guide to Mitigating Spacecraft Charging Effects*, 1st Edition, J. Wiley, 2012.
- [46] M. Burrell, The calculation of proton penetration and dose rates, Nasa Technical Memorandum. George C. Marshall Space Flight Center. Huntsville, Alabama (1964).
- [47] D. Mcalister, *Neutron shielding materials* (2016).
- [48] E. Millour, et. al, The mars climate database (version 5.3), in: *Scientific Workshop: From Mars Express to ExoMars, ESAC, Madrid, Spain, 2018*.
- [49] J. Appelbaum, F. D.J., Solar radiation on mars, *Solar Energy* 45 (6) (1990) 353–363.
- [50] F. Incropera, D. DeWitt, Incropera, F.P. and DeWitt, D.P., 6th Edition, J. Wiley, 2006.
- [51] S. Whitaker, Forced convection heat transfer correlations for flow in pipes, past flat plates, single cylinders, single spheres, and for flow in packed beds and tube bundles, *AIChE Journal* 18 (2) (1972) 361–371.
- [52] R. Osczevski, Martian windchill in terrestrial terms, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 95 (4) (2014) 533–541.
- [53] Carbon dioxide tables, recovered on October 2021 from <http://www.carbon-dioxide-properties.com/CO2TablesWeb.aspx>.
- [54] A. Gómez-San-Juan, Análisis de incertidumbres en sistemas de control térmico en ambientes espaciales, Ph.D. thesis (2018).
- [55] ECSS Secretariat, Ecss-e-hb-31-03a: Thermal analysis handbook (Nov 2016).